

Quantum Interference and Point Versus Interval?

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Newtonian mechanics focuses on a particle as being represented by points, namely the center-of-mass point. This viewpoint seems to be carried over to quantum mechanics where an object, like an electron, is considered to be a point, even though it has a wavelength which governs its probabilistic interactions. In other words, the electron is not a point when it comes to interacting with a 2-slit apparatus, we argue, rather it interacts with both slits leading to a probabilistic treatment of the problem involving both slits. The slits, however, should be about a wavelength apart. As a result, if the initial interaction is thought of in terms of an interval (wavelength or so separation of slits), so the result at the detector should also be thought of in terms of an interval and not a point. The interference pattern at the detector reveals the nature of the interval due to interference. Even though a hit from a particle may occur at a point, there is an overall probability distribution throughout the wavelength region and this is as real a representation of the particle as the hit at a point. Thus, we argue that given the 2-slit interval interaction, it is no surprise that the outcome at the detector also reveals an interval pattern, i.e. the particle is “excluded” from certain minima points. It seems that one is detecting the effects of the interval of interaction at the slits and so it would be surprising if this did not appear at the detector. If one does not expect to see any intensity structure at the detector, then there should be no wavelength effects at the 2-slit apparatus also, but there are. Thus, we argue that one should not be alarmed that a particle is excluded from certain minima points at the detector.

We have tried to argue in previous notes that the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (the probability of a free particle) arises from an attempt to assign equal weight to all e_i, e_j or p_{xi}, p_{xj} (one dimension) pairs (product probabilities) in a free particle two body collision. The probability is complex for a free particle, because there is no real weight among the particles. The x and t appear to allow the probability to be invariant under Lorentz frame changes and also $\delta x \rightarrow -\delta x$, $p \rightarrow -p$. This, however, leads to the notion of conservation in a probability calculation as being violated over a wavelength region or so and not at a point. We argue that when interactions occur involving quantum particles, one must be aware that there is a probability distribution associated with the wavelength and for many test runs, one should see effects of this wavelength as in scattering of spherical potential etc. As a final statement, we argue that one should be overly concerned that quantum particles are “excluded” from certain points on a screen. This happens to define the interference distribution which results already at the 2-slit apparatus and is based on possible probabilistic interactions over the length of a wavelength.

Point Particles

Newtonian particles are usually represented by a center-of-mass point and so for simplicity one thinks of an object as a point, it seems. This idea seems to be carried over into quantum mechanics, with an electron being called a point etc. In Newtonian mechanics, however, interactions also occur at a point, for example in $dx \rightarrow 0$ if one has potential $V(x)$. As a result, the notion of point is key in Newtonian mechanics, but we argue that quantum mechanics differs in terms of certain interactions.

Quantum Free Particle Probability

We have asked in previous notes: Why should one introduce a probability for free particles? In Newtonian mechanics, one has the deterministic $x=vt$ and so where is the probability? We have argued that in two body elastic collisions energy is conserved as well as the required momentum. We suggested that probability arises from a lack of knowledge of outcome energies and momenta (even with conservation) and argued for all e_i, e_j and p_{xi}, p_{xj} (one dimension) pairs with the same sum having the same weight. Thus, one should introduce a probability to account for this lack of discernment of e or p pairs. Furthermore, the probability should be complex because there is no real value weight to a free particle. One has the same "real" weight as another, so to speak. This would at first lead to $\exp(i C E)$ and $\exp(i C^2 p)$, but p is a vector, even in one dimension, and p and $-p$ cannot have different probability values. This suggests introducing another variable so that $p \rightarrow -p$ and variable $\rightarrow -$ variable (due to a change in the direction of the x -axis) leaves probability invariant. This suggests $\exp(i C^2 p \Delta x)$. Given this idea, one may then create a probability which is invariant under Lorentz transformations leading to:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \text{ one dimension } ((1))$$

This leads to the notion of uncertainty in x and t . This is a critical feature, because conservation of momentum and energy are usually thought of as occurring at a point in Newtonian mechanics. We argue that ((1)) suggests that one must consider regions of the size of a wavelength when dealing probabilistically with an interaction. Even if an actual hit occurs at a point, there is still a probability in x given by $\exp(ipx)$ and this is a physical feature.

To see momentum conservation over an interval, one may write:

$$\int dx \exp(-i p_3 x) \exp(-i p_4 x) \exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = 0 \text{ unless } p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4 \text{ (one dimension) } ((2))$$

The integral in ((2)) which yields 0 for $p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4$ ranges over a length linked with $\hbar/(p_3+p_4)$ and $\hbar/(p_1+p_2)$ and so 0 does not emerge for a point. In other words, quantum interactions involve a wavelength distribution and there is no reason why one should not see effects of this in an experiment. In other words, one cannot simply think in terms of points, we argue.

Two-Slit Interference

We try to demonstrate the above ideas by considering the two-slit interference experiment. If a quantum particle interacted as a point, as in Newtonian mechanics, it would simply pass through one slit or the other and there would be no probability involved. We have argued, however, that there is uncertainty of the order of a wavelength \hbar/p from $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$, in turn, is introduced to ensure equal product probabilities for all p_{xi}, p_{xj} pairs with the same sum. If two

slits are separated by about a wavelength, there is a probability for a probabilistic interaction with both slits. In other words, one cannot know which point interaction occurs or through which slit the particle passes, even though it only passes through one. One must perform a probabilistic calculation, following the usual AND/OR features of probability.

Before doing so, however, we consider an important feature of ((2)), i.e. the form $\exp(ipx)$ allowing for conservation of momentum through an integral, i.e. consideration over a range of x . We note that:

$$\exp(ipx + i 3.14) = - \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

In other words, x (or Δx) may be increased such that an extra Δx piece multiplied by p equals 3.14 and then yields -1 multiplied by the original $\exp(ipx)$. This is a key result because it means that sums of $\exp(ipx)$'s have the possibility of adding to 0 under an OR condition. This is the case for the 2-slit experiment.

We first note that one thinks in terms of an interval (wavelength-probabilistic) interaction when a quantum particle arrives at the 2-slit apparatus. This is a key physical feature and it is based on a specific interval feature of the length of a wavelength and the $\exp(ipx)$ probability of the free particle. A priori, there is no reason why the interval feature (present at the start) should not also be present at the detectors on a screen far away. In terms of interaction, the interaction is probabilistic and involves an interval (wavelength). Even if a certain test run has a particle strike a point on the detector screen, many runs could display features of the probabilistic interval interaction with the 2-slit apparatus, we argue. In fact, this is what seems to happen. Furthermore, a single particle hit may still be governed by the overall probabilistic $\exp(ipx)$ feature, as is the case. In other words, even a single run does not lead to a particle striking minimal points at the detector. The probabilistic view still applies at the single particle run level.

Consider solving the 2-slit problem using probability. One has $\exp(ip \cdot r_1)$ for one slit probability and $\exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ for the second. The two are added because this is an OR situation (as in classical probability). Here r_1 is the distance from the center of slit 1 to a point on a screen, and r_2 a vector from the center of slit 2 to the same point. If the screen is very far away, r_1 and r_2 are more or less parallel and if the point is to the left of the center, r_2 is longer than r_1 by:

$d \sin(\theta)$ where d is the slit separation and θ the angle between r_1 (or r_2) and the normal to the slits ((4))

Using $p = \hbar k = \hbar 2\pi/\lambda$ and setting $\hbar = 1$, one has:

$$B = \exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2) = \cos(pr_1) + \cos(pr_1 + p d \sin(\theta))$$

$$+ i (\sin(pr_1) + \sin(pr_1 + p d \sin(\theta))) \quad ((4))$$

If one considers $d \sin(\theta) = (n + 0.5) \lambda$ then for $n = 1$

$$p d \sin(\theta) = 3 \cdot 3.14$$

One may expand $\cos(a+b) = \cos(a)\cos(b) - \sin(a)\sin(b)$ and $\sin(a+b) = \sin(a)\cos(b) + \cos(a)\sin(b)$ ((5))

Then: $\sin(3 \cdot 3.14) = 0$ while $\cos(3 \cdot 3.14) = -1$. This leads to $B=0$ in ((4)). In other words, one does not have a point hit for values of:

$$d \sin(\theta) = (n + .5) \text{ wavelength} \quad ((5))$$

This implies that intervals are established on the screen related to the interval of interaction at the 2-slit apparatus itself. In other words, the 2-slit apparatus measures the probabilistic interactions over a wavelength if one does repeated runs. We suggest that this should be expected and that one should not be alarmed by intervals at the screen or certain minimal points which exclude the particle on the screen. The interaction is probabilistic and based on intervals and this is reflected by the result on the screen, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there seems to be a tendency to think of particles in terms of points. In Newtonian mechanics, the particle is a point, but the interaction also occurs in $dx \rightarrow 0$ (as in the case of a potential $V(x)$) which tends to a point. In quantum mechanics, particles such as an electron (or even a photon) are sometimes thought of as acting at a point. For example, a detector registers the particle at a point or the photoelectric effect shows that one does not have energy spread out over a physical wave.

We argue here that even though a particle may act at a point, it has a wavelength \hbar/p and a probabilistic distribution for interaction linked to this wavelength. Thus, in a 2-slit experiment, right from the beginning one has a probabilistic interaction based on an interval (the separation of the slits which should be about a wavelength apart). The 2-slit experiment measures the probabilistic interaction over such an interval and we argue that one should see evidence of intervals in the outcome at the detector. We suggest that one cannot simply consider the interval at the beginning and then resort to thinking in terms of a point object (electron or photon). The pattern at the detector (far away) shows intervals which are consistent with the interaction at the 2-slit apparatus. Even in a single run of a single particle, $\exp(ipx)$ governs the probabilistic interaction, together with the separation of the slits.

Thus, we argue that it is not unusual that there are minimal points at which the particle does not arrive, as these are linked with defining the interval. The detector result, based on interference of $\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)$ is a probabilistic result based on the probabilistic interaction based on intervals at the 2-slit apparatus. The fact that such a probabilistic interaction occurs seems to be based on the physical property of the particle/photon, namely that it has a wavelength linked to $\exp(ipx)$. This, in turn, is associated with assigning a probability to a free particle (which cannot be real because there is no real weight), but ensures that each e_i, e_j or p_{xi}, p_{xk} pair with the same sum has the same weight in a two body collision.